

Supp. Figure 1.

Supp. Figure 2.

A

B

C

Supp. Figure 3.

A

B

Supp. Figure 4.

A

B

Supp. Figure 5.

Supp. Figure 7

Supp. Figure 8

Supp. Figure 9

Supp. Figure 10

Supp. Figure 11

Supp. Figure 12

Granulocytes
deconvoluted eQTLs

Monocytes (CD14+)
deconvoluted eQTLs

CD4+ T cells
deconvoluted eQTLs

Supp. Figure 13

Granulocytes
deconvoluted eQTLs

Monocytes (CD14+)
deconvoluted eQTLs

CD4+ T cells
deconvoluted eQTLs

Supp. Figure 14

Supp. Figure 15

Supp. Figure 16

Supp. Figure 17

A

B

C

15,616 BIOS whole blood cis-eQTL top effects

Supp. Figure 19

A

B

